

The Event Horizon Telescope Science Gateway - Blackholes, High Throughput Computing, and User Experience Design

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Abstract—The Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) recently used 10 petabyte-scale observation data to construct the first images of blackholes and 100 terabyte-scale simulation data to constrain the plasma properties around supermassive black holes. This work leveraged the Open Science Grid (OSG) high throughput resources provided by the Partnership to Advance Throughput Computing (PATH). While EHT has successfully utilized PATH to create the biggest black hole simulation library to date, the broad adoption of this resource for data processing has been slower. The sophisticated command-line-driven HTCondor environment creates barriers for less technical researchers, limiting PATH’s reach and impact within the wider astronomy and science communities. In May of 2023, the Cyberinfrastructure Integration Research Center (CIRC) at Indiana University was awarded an NSF EAGER award to collaborate with EHT and PATH in implementing a targeted science gateway instance that will integrate three important EHT applications to leverage OSG within the Apache Airavata framework. The proposed session aims to introduce the project and present the progress of the design and development of the EHT Gateway, which will begin on July 1, 2023.

Index Terms—High Throughput Computing, User Experience, Gateways for Science, Astrophysics, Apache Airavata

I. INTRODUCTION

The Partnership to Advance Throughput Computing (PATH) is the NSF’s premier resource for high throughput computing (HTC), delivering over 204 million core hours last year (one-year period ending 13-March 2023) to multi-institutional projects and an additional 164 million core hours to smaller groups that constitute the Open Science Grid (OSG) Connect community [1]. Usage groups include some of the most high-profile research investments by the NSF, such as the multi-institutional Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) collaboration. EHT used 10 petabyte-scale observation data to construct the

first images of black holes and 100 terabyte-scale simulation data to constrain the plasma properties around supermassive black holes. While the EHT has successfully utilized PATH to create the biggest black hole simulation library to date, the broad adoption of this resource is much slower for data processing. The sophisticated OSG command-line-driven environment turns out to be a major barrier to the less technical users, limiting PATH’s reach and impact within the wider astronomy and science communities.

Science gateways [2] have proven to be a successful mechanism for broadening access to scientific cyberinfrastructure (CI) by providing science-centric user environments that are tailored to end-user communities. An emerging and potentially transformative area of research in science gateway development involves the integration of established science gateway technologies with the methodologies of human-computer interactions (HCI) and user experience-based (UX) design.

In order to overcome barriers to adoption and create a highly functional science gateway environment that can effectively utilize the computing power of HTC resources, this project, beginning in July 2023, will focus on the EHT community’s use of PATH as a case study for this methodological approach. The goal of this exploratory project is to demonstrate the effectiveness of combining human-computer interaction design methodologies with science gateway technologies, thereby enhancing the EHT’s analysis of large astronomical data sets. This novel approach has the potential to transform both astrophysics and high throughput computing, offering a fresh perspective that benefits existing PATH user communities and supports the growth of PATH to include new research teams and projects.

Our team consists of experienced leaders from the EHT, HTC, and science gateways communities, bringing together

a wealth of expertise in coupling CI resources with science stakeholder workflows and possessing in-depth knowledge of the EHT ecosystem. Working alongside these leaders are a science gateway developer and a graduate student from the Human-Centered Computing Department at Indiana University as well as a postdoctoral researcher in astronomy from the University of Arizona. Together, we will design, prototype, test, and release an EHT science gateway. The resulting science gateway, to be delivered at the end of this intensive one-year project, will be highly functional and designed to meet the HTC needs for researchers ranging from experienced researchers to students. By prioritizing UX design and emphasizing the necessary human-computer interactions within a science gateway environment, we aim to ensure a positive experience for EHT researchers, fostering continued engagement and reliance on PATH HTC resources.

While this project is short-term and focuses on the EHT collaboration, the foundational work of integrating science gateways with PATH-provided resources has the potential for long-term benefits for both the science gateway and PATH communities. Science gateways will enhance their toolbox of offerings by incorporating high capacity, high availability resources. PATH will add a UX-centric access method, providing an entry point for users unfamiliar with command-line interfaces and with minimal time or effort available to learn new technologies on their path to discovery.

II. EHT SCIENCE GATEWAY PROTOTYPE

During the calendar year of 2022, CIRC collaborated with EHT researchers from the University of Arizona to develop a proof of concept for the EHT gateway [3] as part of the XSEDE Extended Collaborative Support Services program. The proof of concept version demonstrated the basic integration of PATH resources with Apache Airavata, but it lacked the advanced functionality required by a large number of EHT researchers and did not incorporate user requirements or UX design methods. The current project builds on the proof of concept by creating a highly functional multi-application science gateway. This gateway will cater to a large portion of the EHT community and accommodate various levels of analysis tasks.

III. PROJECT OBJECTIVES

This project is divided into three overarching objectives.

- 1) Deliver a highly functional, UX-centric gateway to the EHT project. This gateway will enable the integration of three existing workflows that leverage OSPool resources.
- 2) Address the technical hurdles to allow the utilization of HTC resources from a science gateway environment within the Apache Airavata framework.
- 3) Conduct targeted outreach efforts aimed at astronomy researchers and the CI community to amplify the impact of the project.

IV. THE EVENT HORIZON TELESCOPE GATEWAY

The prototype EHT gateway described previously allowed single runs of the ipole application on PATH resources and was demonstrated in a collaboration-wide training webinar. The proposed work will extend this prototype to launch large-scale parameter sweeps from science gateways on PATH. Three EHT applications have been identified for integration. These are 1) the black hole image simulation workflow utilizing ipole, as mentioned above, 2) a synthetic data generation pipeline using SYMBA, and 3) an image reconstruction pipeline.

Fig. 1. Black hole simulation library generated for interpreting the image of the supermassive black hole at the center of the Milky Way. The computation was done on PATH-provided resources.

V. USER EXPERIENCE DESIGN (UXD)

Given the high-risk, high-reward nature of this proposed work and the limited timeline, we will solicit concrete user research requirements and incorporate them into the system design. To achieve this, we will leverage best practices in User Experience (UX) design, capturing the subtleties of the core use cases. Our approach will be based on the double-diamond design process, which involves divergent and convergent thinking to generate and validate design solutions. Through this process, we will design interfaces for the aforementioned three applications.

During the initial divergence and convergence phase, we will gather and analyze user and stakeholder requirements, deriving meaningful research insights. In the subsequent divergence and convergence phase, we will validate design ideas, develop prototypes, and conduct testing with end-users. To comprehensively understand and address identifiable challenges, we will communicate and engage with EHT stakeholders, ensuring that our design solutions effectively address their needs. Proven UX methods such as cognitive task analysis and user interviews will be employed to enhance the design process.

VI. INTEGRATION WITH APACHE AIRAVATA

Our project seeks to implement a web-based science gateway that leverages the open source Apache Airavata [4] framework and builds upon the proof of concept EHT Gateway. The primary objective is to provide users with a streamlined and user-friendly interface for interacting with PATH resources,

eliminating the challenges associated with command-line interfaces for users without programming experience. By implementing an Apache Airavata-based gateway with a graphical user interface (GUI), we will significantly reduce the learning curve associated with command-line interfaces, enabling more researchers to utilize HTC resources effectively. The web interface will be designed to be user friendly, providing clear instructions and visual aids to guide users through the process. This will make the system more accessible to researchers with varying levels of technical proficiency. Web-based interfaces provided by Apache Airavata have proved highly effective, allowing researchers to more quickly and efficiently utilize high performance computing (HPC) environments than traditional command-line interfaces. Moreover, the OSPool—accessible through Apache Airavata middleware—provides hundreds of thousands of hours of daily access to HTC resources, further enhancing its appeal to the scientific community. While cou-

projects that could benefit from the collaborative PATH and CIRC relationship. To expand our outreach efforts, the project team will specifically target EHT user groups at semiannual, in-person EHT collaboration meetings as well as through an online tutorial webinar event that we will organize. These outreach events will feature tutorials focused on increasing the user base and identifying user needs for future functionality. In 2024, we plan to submit tutorials at PEARC and the Science Gateways conference. We will also initiate engagements with two additional PATH-recommended communities that are currently using HTC resources but are likely to embrace science gateways. By strategically targeting these events and communities, we aim to enhance user engagement, expand the user base, and identify opportunities for collaboration and future development within the PATH framework.

A. Collaboration

The project receives dedicated effort and oversight from the funded institutions of Indiana University and the University of Arizona. Additional community technical and research support will be provided by the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, MIT Haystack Observatory, the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, and the Harvard Black Hole Initiative. To further strengthen the project, we will leverage support and operational assistance of the PATH team from the University of Wisconsin–Madison and Morgridge Institute for Research. This collaboration entails hosting an OSPool Access Point and providing support for HTCondor integration issues that may arise throughout the project’s duration.

Fig. 2. A depiction of the proposed EHT science gateway, which will enable users to interact with Apache Airavata’s gateway services and access the OSPool through HTCondor access points.

pling the Apache Airavata science gateway framework with PATH resources is an undoubtedly significant advancement and beneficial to both the HTC and Apache Airavata communities, it requires substantial effort to fully integrate the two systems beyond a mere proof of concept. Our project aims to provide a highly integrated EHT portal while recording and addressing the challenges of interactions between web-based environments and HTC workload creation and submission. By addressing these challenges, we seek to streamline the adoption process for future projects that leverage these technologies. This, in turn, will enable the seamless utilization of HTC resources within science gateway environments. The project will draw upon the insights gained from the EHT integration and concurrent survey work of PATH by SGX3, the Science Gateway Center of Excellence. This collaborative effort will establish a strong foundation for supporting additional research communities. These communities will be identified jointly by the PATH project leadership, the science gateways community, and the management of this project.

VII. TRAINING AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

The PATH team and the CIRC team at IU conducted joint tutorials throughout the 2022 calendar year. This included delivering an EHT-targeted webinar in September and conducting a tutorial at the Gateways 2022 conference in October. Building upon these events, we will further refine the materials and continue to provide training at CI events and target existing

VIII. PROJECT DELIVERABLES

The project receives dedicated effort and oversight from the funded institutions of Indiana University and the University of Arizona. Additional community technical and research support will be provided by the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, MIT Haystack Observatory, the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, and the Harvard Black Hole Initiative. To further strengthen the project, we will leverage support and operational assistance of the PATH team from the University of Wisconsin–Madison and Morgridge Institute for Research. This collaboration entails hosting an OSPool Access Point and providing support for HTCondor integration issues that may arise throughout the project’s duration.

IX. COLLABORATION

The principal project deliverable will be a fully functional EHT Science Gateway. This gateway will support the EHT needs for preparing and submitting black hole image simulation (ipole), synthetic data generation (SYMBA), and image reconstruction (ehtim) with PATH resources. A significant amount of effort will be concentrated on user experience (UX) design, allowing these applications to be widely usable by EHT scientists through science gateway user interfaces. We will integrate the lessons learned from the UX-based

design and development of the EHT science gateway and outputs from efforts within SGX3 to integrate new science gateway portals that leverage HTC resources. These may include additional astronomy communities (such as the Vera Rubin Observatory), and other current OSPool users identified by our PATH collaborators. We will present this work at both cyberinfrastructure-focused conferences (PEARC, OSG All Hands, Gateways) and to the multi-messenger astronomy community (Semi-annual EHT Collaboration Meetings). These outreach deliverables will include developer and user tutorials and training events.

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